

Impact of Skill Development Initiatives on Employment Creation in Uttar Pradesh's Rohilkhand Region

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Abstract

Today's age is the competitive age of globalization, where skill is an important tool and instrument to increase the efficiency, quality of labour for productivity and social and economic growth. The skill is a very strong tool for the empowerment of an individual and to have social acceptability in the community to which he or she belongs. Primary or secondary data used in this study of this research paper. Primary data was collected from 240 respondents from four districts, including Bareilly, Badaun, Moradabad, and Rampur, and secondary data was from various research papers and journals. This study examines the role of skill development programs in reducing unemployment in backward areas in the Rohilkhand regions. In the conclusion of this paper, it was found that, India's youthful population, which makes up the majority of the workforce, presents a special opportunity. Workforce skill development is essential to lowering unemployment rates, filling the skills gaps in the labour market, and meeting the growing need for skilled workers in India's changing economy. A multifaceted strategy comprising government funding, private sector partnership, raised awareness, better training quality, and ongoing outcome assessment is needed to address these concerns. India can improve its worker empowerment and training ecosystem for a more affluent future by addressing these issues.

Keywords : Skill Development, Unemployment, Labour Force, Employment.

Introduction:

Unemployment is a major problem in the backward areas of India. Most of the population is living below the poverty line in rural areas. The people have to struggle a lot to fulfil their basic needs and their standard of living is very poor. Lot of people is migrating from rural to urban areas in get of employment opportunities. Day by day the urban areas population is rising and rural population is declining. There are many reasons for the migration of rural population but Unemployment is important major reasons. Most of the population of India lives in rural areas and depends on agriculture for their livelihood. Agriculture sector provides limited employment opportunities. Hence there is a need to promote skill development in the rural sector (Prasad, at al 2017)¹.

Education plays an important role in mold a skill-based society in India. If the youth of rural areas are given skill education, it will lead to both economic prosperity and social development. In today's time there is a need for skilled population all over the world. The skill development level and educational attainment of the population determine the income level and the adaptability of the working class. If the rural youth of India are given skill training, it will reduce unemployment and along with-it migration from rural areas to urban areas will also reduce (Zenou, 2010)².

Important actions have been taken by the Indian government to address these issues. Established the Skill Development Mission in 2010 after creating the first Skill Development Policy in 2009. Established in 2014, Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship operates through the Directorate of Training (DT) and National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) (Mshengu, 2005)³. Apart from this, there are many other important schemes of Union and State government which are promoting skill development. Such as Uttar Pradesh Skill Development Mission, Deendayal Upadhyay Gramin Kaushal yojana etc (Singh, at al 2018)⁴.

Review of Literature:

In their study "Promoting Rural Entrepreneurship through Skill Development programme for Decent Livelihood: A Review," (Tripathi and Singh, 2017)⁵ examined the necessity of fostering rural entrepreneurship through skill development in order to support rural livelihoods. Food processing and food value addition jobs are created by entrepreneurship in rural areas. It contributes to both rural poverty reduction and rural development.

Findings of this study indicate that there is a significant need for technical skills among rural children since they lack them. Establishing businesses in rural areas should inspire women and young people to take part in the country's economic development. Villager migration can be halted by rural business.

A study on "The Scope of Skill Development programme, Employability of Indian Workforce in Context of Make in India" was carried out by Deka and Batra (2016)⁶. The impact of the Make in India initiative on skill development and employability has been examined in this study report. The question of how the current skilled workforce differs from the needed skilled workforce has also been investigated in this study report. This research has two primary goals. The data used in this investigation is secondary. Numerous libraries and government websites, including Make in India and Skill India, have gathered the data.

The author claims that both domestic and foreign industries may generate jobs through the Make in India initiative. There is a need for 22 million trained adolescents, but just 10% of the workforce has formal training. It is essential to implement a number of skill development programs to close the skill gap between the necessary and available skills for the Made in India program to succeed.

The elements impacting employees' perceptions of reskilling programs in the IT field were highlighted by Singh and Sanjeev (2016)⁷ in their study "Need for re-skill training towards Make in India initiative." Among the factors that have been discovered are value addition, need orientation, soft skill training, and appropriate skill training. KMO and Bartlett's test have been used to evaluate the metric ton forward growth rate that has been constructed. The results of this study indicate that the factors analyzed are impacting employees' attitudes.

Hazarika (2016)⁸ examined the skill development resources offered for rural entrepreneurship in her work, "Skill Development for Rural Entrepreneurship: A Study on State Institute of Rural Development (SIRD), Assam." The motivational function of the training offered by the Assamese institute is also examined in this paper. Resource Center, Common Facility Development, Development and Management Growth Center, IT Motivational Infrastructure Resource Center, etc., have all been covered in this research report. According to the research paper's conclusion, Assam's enterprise development is relatively low because of a lack of awareness.

Programs for skill development greatly improve young people's employability in the service industry in the Rohilkhand region. Numerous studies have provided evidence that these programs increase participants' income levels and job satisfaction in addition to improving job acquisition rates. Effect on Employment Rates It has been demonstrated that vocational training raises employment rates; 70% of trained people land jobs, compared to 50% of untrained people (Bhatt et al., 2024)⁹. Uttarakhand has a very high youth unemployment rate of almost 20%, highlighting the necessity of successful skill development programs to close this gap (Chakraborty, 2023)¹⁰.

Financial Gains with median monthly salaries of INR 18,000 compared to INR 14,000 for untrained individuals, skilled individuals enjoy a 29% wage premium (Bhatt et al., 2024). For trained individuals, skill development programs average 7% yearly income growth, which helps sustain income growth (Bhatt et al., 2024)¹¹.

Obstacles and Suggestions:

Effective employment outcomes are hampered by the continued gap between career counseling and skill development, despite breakthroughs (Kumar & Hooda, 2024)¹². To maximize program efficacy, policymakers must improve public-private partnerships and match training curriculum with industry demands (Bhatt et al., 2024). On the other hand, whereas skill development initiatives exhibit potential, obstacles including inadequate infrastructure and restricted financial resources continue to exist, which may compromise their efficacy in specific populations (Kumar, 2024)¹³.

Objectives:

1. To know the employment status of skilled and non-skilled peoples in Rohilkhand Region of Rural Areas.
2. To understand the barriers in acquiring skill development in rural areas.

Methodology and Database used:

Primary or secondary data used in this study of this research paper. Primary data was collected from Rohilkhand Regions of Uttar Pradesh and secondary data was collected from various research papers and journals. Rohilkhand Regions Located in the northwest of Uttar Pradesh, India, and concentrated on the Bareilly and Moradabad divisions, there is a region known as Rohilkhand (Bareilly, Moradabad, Badaun, and Rampur).

Four districts of the Rohilkhand region have been selected for data collection, including Bareilly, Badaun, Moradabad, and Rampur districts. Interviews were conducted through questionnaires from 60 respondents from each district who received skill development education and training through the Industrial Training Institute (ITI), Government Technical Institute (GTI), Deen Dayal Upadhyay Skill Development Programme (DDUSDP), Uttar Pradesh Skill Development Programme (UPSDP) and National Skill Development Programme (NSDP). Each district was divided into 4 zones East, West,

North, and South zone for data collection. Data has been collected through a questionnaire from 15 respondents from each area of the district. The total respondents are 240 (120 Skilled People and 120 Non-Skilled People total 240 respondents) from Rohilkhand region Districts (Bareilly, Badaun, Moradabad, and Rampur). This study has collectively analyzed the data of the Rohilkhand region.

The Effect of Skill Development Programmes on Employment Generation:

Figure 1 : Employment Status of Respondents (Skilled Peoples -Y) in Rohilkhand Regions of Rural Areas

Sources: Primary Data of Rohilkhand Regions

Figure 1 show the analysis based on data from Table – 1, 120 respondents are skilled in vocational Education along with ITI, GTI, DDUSDP, UPSDP, and NSDP. In Figure 4, the Employment Status of Skilled Peoples –Y is shown sector-wise with the government sector, Private Sector, Self-Employment, Agriculture Sector, Labour class, and Unemployed on the X axis and vocational Education as ITI, GTI, DDUSDP, UPSDP, and NSDP are shown on the Y axis with the number of peoples who got employment.

Among the skilled people who have ITI qualifications, 4 people are employed in the government sector, 6 people are employed in the private sector, 7 are self-employed, 3 are employed in the agricultural sector and 2 are employed as laborers. And the unemployment rate among those having ITI qualifications is zero. Among those who qualify for GTI, 10 people have got employment in the government sector, 16 people have got employment in the private sector, 10 people are self-employed, and 4 people are employed in the agricultural sector. The number of people doing labour work is zero but 2 are unemployed because they do not work for themselves and instead of working as laborers, they are in search of employment.

Among those eligible for DDUSDP, 6 people are employed in the government sector, 20 people are employed in the private sector, 4 are self-employed, 2 are employed in the agriculture sector and 1 is employed as a wage laborer. 3 people are unemployed. The unemployment rate is higher among those who qualify for DDUSDP. Among those who are skilled with UPSDP, 2 people are employed in the government sector, 5 people are employed in the private sector, 2 are self-employed, 1 is employed in the agriculture sector and 2 are employed as labourers. 4 people are unemployed. The unemployment rate is high among those having UPSDP qualifications. Among those who are skilled with NSDP, 1 person has got employment in the private sector, 2 people are self-employed and 1 person is unemployed. 1 person works less in the agriculture sector and 2 people work on wages and 4 people are unemployed. Those having NSDP qualifications have not got any employment in the government sector nor do they work in the agriculture sector or as laborers.

Table 1 : Impact of Skill Development Programme (Skilled Peoples –Y) on Employment and Unemployment in Rural Areas

Skilled People (Y)	Employment	Unemployment
22	17	5
42	36	6
36	30	6
16	9	7
4	3	1

Correlation between Skilled People (Y) and Employment & Unemployment (in %)

	Skilled People (Y)	Employment	Unemployment
Skilled People (Y)	1	.992** .001	.655 .230
Employment	.992** .001	1	.553 .333
Unemployment	.655 .230	.655 .333	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 2 : Employment Status of Respondents (Non-Skilled Peoples -X) in Rohilkhand Regions of Rural Areas

Sources: Primary Data of Rohilkhand Regions

Figure 2 shows the analysis based on data from Table – 2, 120 respondents are Non-skilled People with Traditional and Non-Vocational Education as Middle (8th Class), Secondary, Higher Secondary, Graduate, and Post-graduate. In Figure 5, the Employment Status of Non-Skilled Peoples –X is shown sector-wise with the government sector, Private Sector, Self-Employment, Agriculture Sector, Labour class, and Unemployed on the X axis and Traditional and Non-Vocational Education as Middle (8th Class), Secondary, Higher Secondary, Graduate, and Post-graduate are shown on the Y axis with the number of people who got employment.

Among the non-skilled people who have Middle (8th Class) qualifications, zero people are employed in the government sector, 6 people are employed in the private sector, 3 are self-employed, 6 are employed in the agricultural sector, 2 are employed as labourers and 3 people are unemployed. Among those who have people Secondary Education, 2 people have got employment in the government sector, 10 people have got employment in the private sector, 2 people are self-employed, and 5 people are employed in the agricultural sector. The 9 people are doing labour work and 2 people are unemployed.

Among those who have people Higher Secondary Education, 4 people are employed in the government sector, 12 people are employed in the private sector, 4 are self-employed, 8 are employed in the agriculture sector and 6 people are employed as wage labourers. 4 people are unemployed. Among those who have people Graduate Degree, 3 people are employed in the government sector, 5 people are employed in the private sector, 6 are self-employed, 4 is employed in the agriculture sector and zero people are as labourers. 4 people are unemployed. Among those who have people Post Graduate Degree, 1 people are employed in the government sector, 3 peoples have got employment in the private sector, 2 people are self-employed and anybody are not working in Agriculture and Labourers class and 2 people are unemployed.

People who have skill development education like through ITI, GTI, DDUSDP, UPSDP, and NSDP have a very low rate of unemployment. People who have only Traditional and Non-Vocational Education as Middle, (8th Class) Secondary, Higher Secondary, Graduate, and Post-graduate education, the unemployment rate is very high. Among those people who have higher education, they do not want to work in the agriculture sector and as labour class.

Results or Finding:

The analysis of 120 respondents in vocational education shows that 4 people with ITI qualifications are employed in the government sector, 6 in the private sector, 7 are self-employed, 3 are in the agricultural sector, and 2 are employed as labourers. The unemployment rate is zero for those with

ITI qualifications. Similarly, 10 people with GTI qualifications have employment in the government sector, 16 in the private sector, 10 are self-employed, and 4 are in the agricultural sector. The unemployment rate is higher for those with DDUSDP qualifications. Lastly, 1 person with NSDP qualifications has employment in the private sector, 2 are self-employed, and 1 is unemployed.

Traditional and non-vocational education and Employment Generation:

The analysis of 120 respondents reveals that despite having traditional and non-vocational education, only a small number of them are employed in government sector. Among those with Middle (8th Class) qualifications, no one is employed in government sector. Among those with Secondary Education, two are employed in government sector, while the remaining nine are employed in the private sector. Among those with Higher Secondary Education, four are employed in the government sector, while the remaining four are employed in the private sector. Among those with Post Graduate Degrees, one is employed in the government sector, three in the private sector, two are self-employed.

Barriers in Acquiring Skill Development in Rural Areas:

Supply and Demand Unbalanced, due to the imbalance in the demand and supply of manpower by the industries, various types of skill development initiatives are being expanded by the government, NSDC, private it is. Only a small portion of the workforce in India received various vocational and technical training for skill development.

At lower skills there are more job seekers than the number of job position available while at higher skills there are few job seekers than the number of position available. This imbalance in demand and supply shows that there is a huge gap between formal education and training required to acquire skills in demand by industries.

Problems of Geographical

The diverse geographical structure across different states and union territories in the country also harms the labour market. Employment generation is higher in economically developed states, whereas employment generation is lower in state with less economic development thus, states with higher economic development have to depend on workers from other geographical areas. Most vocational and technical training facilities are provided in urban areas. Therefore, youth from rural areas lag behind in getting skill training.

Lack of vocational training and formal education

India has made progress in primary education, but is lagging behind in higher education. Vocational and training institute are largely supported by government and private entities. The available capacity for industrial training is less than the industrial requirement of skilled workforce. Most female student dropout of education at an average age of 15 years. This is coupled with poor literacy and outdated training which fails to meet industrial needs.

Skill development for women's

The share of women employees in India is much lower than in Brazil and China. A large portion of the female workforce is engaged in unorganized work due to which women fail to get skilled jobs. A large number of women workers in India are unskilled and lack both basic education and vocational educational training. A large number of women in both urban and rural areas have failed to attain primary education. Currently, majority of the women workforce in India is unskilled

Placement Related Challenges

The absence of a connection between education and the employment of the skilled labor is a significant issue with India's existing skill development system. Most ITI and ICT do not provide job placement services due to which youth struggle to find proper employment. The lack of connection between the demand of the local economy and the skills provided by local institutions creates employment gaps. Due to this, job related migration increases.

Private Sector Participation

Most of the private sector training institutes are located in urban areas; therefore the rural population lags behind. Additionally, the weaker groups cannot receive adequate skill training because of the high expense of these institutions.

Recommendations/Suggestions:

- **Emphasis on Emerging Technologies:** To address the needs of the labour market of the future, incorporate training Programmes for cutting-edge fields like data science, renewable energy, and artificial intelligence

- Establish and support skill development centers around the nation to offer easily accessible training options for various industries.
- Training Programmes for Trainers: To enhance their abilities and guarantee the provision of high-quality training, hold frequent training sessions for trainers and instructors.
- Financial Incentives: Provide monetary rewards, such as tax breaks and subsidies, to people and companies who engage in skill development.
- Public-Private Partnerships: Promote public-private collaborations to pool resources and knowledge for successful skill-development Programmes.

Conclusions:

In the competitive era of globalization, skill is a crucial tool for improving labour quality, efficiency, and efficacy for social and economic advancement as well as productivity. Skill is a very strong tool for the empowerment of an individual and to have social acceptability in the community to which he or she belongs. However, when we try to find out the status of skill development programmes run by the government, we have to think over it again since there are so many lacunas from the start of these schemes and programmes, execution and implementation and evaluation level. India's youthful population, which makes up the majority of the workforce, presents a special opportunity. By 2026, around 63% of India's population will be in the working age range. But at 6.6 percent, our youth unemployment rate is far higher than the 2.2 percent national unemployment average. In India, almost 10 million people join the workforce annually. Of our population, 58% are younger than 29. Our country is in the developing stage and 25 percent of the population is at a very young stage below the age of 25, but are unskilled. Being unskilled youth, they are not able to attain appropriate employment.

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